

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

5 ЖИЛД, 6 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

ТОМ 5, НОМЕР 6

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 5, ISSUE 6

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА | INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

№6 (2022) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9297-2022-6>

Бош муҳаррир:

Тўхтасинов Илҳом

п.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Бош муҳаррир ўринбосари:

Главный редактор:

Тухтасинов Илхом

д.п.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Заместитель главного редактора:

Editor in Chief:

Tuhtasinov Ilhom

DSc. Professor (Uzbekistan)

Deputy Chief Editor

ТАҲРИРИЙ МАСЛАҲАТ КЕНГАШИ

Назаров Бахтиёр

академик. (Ўзбекистон)

Якуб Умарўғли

ф.ф.д., профессор (Туркия)

Алмаз Улви Биннатова

ф.ф.д., профессор (Озарбайжон)

Бокиева Гуландом

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Миннуллин Ким

ф.ф.д., профессор (Татаристон)

Махмудов Низомиддин

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Керимов Исмаил

ф.ф.д., профессор (Россия)

Жўраев Маматкул

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Куренов Рахиммаед

к.ф.н. (Туркменистон)

Кристофер Жеймс Форт

Мичиган университети (АҚШ)

Умархўжаев Мухтор

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Мирзаев Ибодулло

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Болтабоев Ҳамидулла

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Дўстмухаммедов Хуршид

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Лиходзиевский А.С.

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Сиддиқова Ирода

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Шиукашвили Тамар

ф.ф.д. (Грузия)

Юсупов Ойбек

масъул котиб, доцент (Ўзбекистон)

РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ СОВЕТ

Назаров Бахтиёр

академик. (Узбекистан)

Якуб Умар оглы

д.ф.н., профессор (Туркия)

Алмаз Улви Биннатова

д.ф.н., профессор (Азербайджан)

Бакиева Гуландом

д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Миннуллин Ким

д.ф.н., профессор (Татарстан)

Махмудов Низомиддин

д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Керимов Исмаил

д.ф.н., профессор (Россия)

Джураев Маматкул

д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Куренов Рахыммаед

к.ф.н. (Туркменистан)

Кристофер Джеймс Форт

Университет Мичигана (США)

Умархаджаев Мухтар

д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Мирзаев Ибодулло

д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Балтабоев Ҳамидулла

д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Дустмухаммедов Хуршид

д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Лиходзиевский А.С.

д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Сиддиқова Ирода

д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Шиукашвили Тамар

д.ф.н. (Грузия)

Юсупов Ойбек

отв. секретарь, доцент (Узбекистан)

EDITORIAL BOARD

Bakhtiyor Nazarov

academician. (Uzbekistan)

Yakub Umarogli

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Turkey)

Almaz Ulvi Binnatova

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Azerbaijan)

Bakieva Gulandom

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Minnulin Kim

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Tatarstan)

Mahmudov Nizomiddin

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Kerimov Ismail

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Russia)

Juraev Mamatkul

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Kurenov Rakhimmamed

Ph.D. Ass. Prof. (Turkmenistan)

Christopher James Fort

University of Michigan (USA)

Umarkhodjaev Mukhtar

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Mirzaev Ibodulla

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Boltaboev Hamidulla

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Dustmuhammedov Khurshid

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Lixodzievsky A.S.

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Siddiqova Iroda

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Shiukashvili Tamar

Doc. of philol. scien. (Georgia)

Yusupov Oybek

Ass. prof. (Uzbekistan) - Senior Secretary

PageMaker | Верстка | Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz

ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,

улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz

Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,

Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz

Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

1. Daminova Orzigul INGLIZ TILIDA ASPEKTUALLIK XUSUSIDA.....	5
2. Isaqova Munisa XALQARO HUQUQIY TERMINLARNING LESIKOGRAFIK TALQINI.....	10
3. Baxodirova Shaxlo ABDULLA QODIRIYNING LEKSIKOGRAFIYA BORASIDAGI FAOLIYATI, QARASHLARI.....	15
4. Ганиева Дилдорахон МОДАЛ ВА КЎМАКЧИ ФЕЪЛЛАРНИНГ СИНКРЕТИК ҲАМДА ПОЛИФУНКЦИОНАЛ ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ.....	22
5. Bayram Bilir O‘RXUN BITIKLARIDA I HARFI VA YOPIQ E TOVUSHINING YEVROPALIK VA RUS TURKOLOGLARI TOMANIDAN TRANSKRIPSIYASI.....	25
6. Jumanova Shohista TARJIMONNING YUTUQ VA KAMCHILIKLARI (CHO‘L PONNING “KECHA VA KUNDUZ” ASARI MISOLIDA).....	29
7. Сулайманова Нилуфар ВОЗНИКНОВЕНИЕ КАТЕГОРИИ ЭМОЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ОЦЕНКИ В ИМПЛИЦИТНОЙ ФОРМЕ.....	34
8. Хазраткулиён Дилшодаи Фарходзод ЎЗБЕКИСТОН ТОЖИК АДАБИЁТИДА МАДЕҲА ШЕЪРИ РИВОЖИ ҲАКИДА.....	43
9. Qodirova Fazilat, Ayakulov Nurbek, Ayakulova Aziza PROBLEMS OF SYNONYMY AND ANTONYMY OF TERMS – THEORETICAL REVIEW.....	50
10. Ахмедова Дилдора ЎЗБЕК ТИЛИНИНГ ЭТИМОЛОГИК ЛУҒАТИ – КОРПУС СЕМАНТИК КЕНГАЙТМАСИНИНГ АХБОРОТ БАЗАСИ.....	54
11. Абдусаламова Лобар Акбар кизи ЧИНГИЗ АЙТМАТОВ ИЖДИНИ ДАВРЛАШТИРИШ МАСАЛАСИГА ДОИР: ОДОРОКОЛОРИСТИК МОТИВЛАРНИ ЎРГАНИШ АСПЕКТИДА.....	59
12. Yusupova Guzal Rashitovna NARRATIV TRANSFORMATSIYALAR NI KOYA NUTQINI MODELLASHTIRISHNING ASOSIY VOSITALARIDAN BIRI SIFATIDA.....	64
13. Раупова Мухайё Насировна ОБРАТНЫЙ ПЕРЕВОД КАК СПОСОБ ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ СТЕПЕНИ АДЕКВАТНОСТИ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ ПЕРЕВОДЧЕСКИХ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЙ).....	70
14. Fayzulloyeva Zilola Zafarovna BADDIY MATN XUSUSIYATLARI VA UNING TARJIMASIDAGI QIYINCHILIKLARI.....	76
15. Хидирова Мухлиса Алишер кизи “ЖАЛЛОД КЎШИҒИ” ҲУЖАТЛИ РОМАНИДА ОИЛАНИНГ ИЖТИМОИЙ-СИЁСИЙ ҲАЁТДАГИ ЎРНИ.....	82
16. Воситов Валижон Абдувахобович XVI-XVIII ASRLARDA TURKIY SŪZLAR INGLIZLAR NI GOҲIDA.....	89
17. Burknonova Aziza Ihtiyorovna THE IMPORTANCE OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN LEARNING AND TEACHING A SECOND LANGUAGE.....	96
18. Norova Mavluda Fayzulloyevna STYLISTIC-SEMANTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF WORDS WITH SOUND CHANGE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES.....	102

19. Giyasova Dilafruz Xamzaevna MUAYYAN MAQSADLAR UCHUN INGLIZ TILI DARSLARIDA INGLIZ TILINI O'RGATISHDA TINGLASH KO'NIKMALARINING AHAMIYATI.....	108
20. Sadri Sa'diev, Fariduni Farhodzod (Yuldashev) БУГУНГИ ВА КЕЛАЖАК АВЛОДГА МУРОЖААТНОМА ЁХУД БИР ШЕЪРКИМ, МАНГУЛИККА ДАХЛДОР.....	112
21. Махаммадов Бобир Исан ўғли ИНГЛИЗ ТИЛИДАГИ АНДРОИД ОПЕРАЦИОН ТИЗИМИ МОБИЛЬ ИЛОВАЛАРИ (АОТМИ) ТЕРМИНЛАРИНИНГ СТРУКТУР ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ.....	115
22. Хаитов Мурод Атаназарович, Абдуллаев Ибодулла Қочқарович ИЧКИ ИШЛАР ОРГАНЛАРИ ХОДИМЛАРИ ОРАСИДА КАСАЛЛАНИШ ВА УНИ КЕЛТИРИБ ЧИҚАРУВЧИ ОМИЛЛАРНИНГ ТИББИЙ-ИЖТИМОЙ ЖИХАТЛАРИ.....	122
23. Икрамова Шахло Абдурасуловна ПРОБЛЕМЫ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ СОЦИАЛЬНОГО КОМПОНЕНТА ЗНАЧЕНИЯ СЛОВА.....	130
24. Мамасолиев Илхам Убайдуллаевич НОВЫЕ СЛОВА И СОЧЕТАНИЯ В РУССКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ В ПЕРИОД РАСПРОСТРАНЕНИЯ КОРОНОВИРУСНОЙ ИНФЕКЦИИ (на материале средств массовой информации).....	135
25. Миралимова Шахзода Хасанбоевна ИНТЕРНЕТ – МУЛОҚОТНИНГ ЯНГИЧА ТИЗИМИ.....	141
26. Худойбергана Д.С., Абдурахимова Ф.Б. ОЛАМНИНГ ЛИСОНИЙ МАНЗАРАСИГА ИЛМИЙ ЁНДАШУВЛАР.....	147
27. Abduraximova Taxmina Toxirjonovna, Kodirova Mukaddas Tog'ayevna INGLIZ TILIDA GENDERNING LEKSIK IFODASI.....	153
28. Izzatbek Rejapov SON KOMPONENTLI FRAZEOLOGIK BIRLIKLARNING MAVZUIY-SEMANTIK TAHLILI.....	158
29. Ниёзова Шоира Тоировна ҚИЁСИЙ ЛИНГВИСТИКАНИНГ ФАН СИФАТИДА ШАКЛЛАНИШИ.....	165
30. Abduraximova Taxmina Toxirjonovna, Kodirova Mukaddas Tog'ayevna INGLIZ TILIDA GENDERNING LEKSIK IFODASI.....	170
31. Бабахаджаев Рашид Хашимович ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫХ МЕТОДОВ НА ИНОСТРАННЫХ ЯЗЫКАХ.....	175
32. Жумаева Дилноза Бахшуллоевна АНТРОПОНИМИК МУРОЖААТ БИРЛИКЛАРИ ВА УЛАРНИНГ НУТҚИЙ-МАВЗУИЙ ТУРЛАРИ.....	180
33. Ваымуродова Laylo Кахрамоновна NUTQIY FAOLIYAT VA NUTQIY STRATEGIYANING PRAGMATIK IFODASI.....	185

ISSN: 2181-9297

www.tadqiqot.uz

Giyasova Dilafruz XamzaevnaSamarqand davlat chet tillar instituti katta o'qituvchisi
giyasovadilafruzsam@gmail.com**MUAYYAN MAQSADLAR UCHUN INGLIZ TILI DARSLARIDA INGLIZ TILINI
O'RGATISHDA TINGLASH KO'NIKMALARINING AHAMIYATI** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7393835>**ANNOTASIYA**

ESL o'qituvchilari orasida tinglab tushunish ikkinchi tilni o'zlashtirishda muhim ahamiyatga ega ekanligi va shuning uchun tinglash ko'nikmalariga o'rgatish kerak degan ishonch ortib bormoqda. Maqolada tinglash ko'nikmalarining ahamiyati va uning ESL darslarida ingliz tilini o'rgatishdagi roli o'rganiladi. Maqolada o'qituvchilar tomonidan qo'llaniladigan turli xil o'qitish usullarining ijobiy va salbiy tomonlari ko'rsatilgan va tinglashni boshqa nuqtai nazardan o'rgatish qanchalik muhimligi, masalan, yuqori va past kontekst madaniyatini bilish, aqlli va beparvo tinglash to'siqlari.

Kalit so'zlar: malaka, muloqot, til, o'qitish usullari, tushunish

Гиясова Дилафруз ХамзаевнаСтарший преподаватель Самаркандский
государственный институт иностранных языков
giyasovadilafruzsam@gmail.com**ВАЖНОСТЬ НАВЫКОВ АУДИРОВАНИЯ ПРИ ОБУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ
ЯЗЫКУ НА УРОКАХ АНГЛИЙСКИЙ ДЛЯ ОСОБЫХ ЦЕЛЕЙ****АННОТАЦИЯ**

Преподаватели ESL все больше убеждаются в том, что понимание аудирования играет ключевую роль в овладении вторым языком, и поэтому навыкам аудирования следует обучать. В статье исследуется важность навыков аудирования и их роль в обучении английскому языку на уроках ESL. В статье приводятся плюсы и минусы различных подходов к обучению, используемых учителями, и исследуется, насколько важно обучение аудированию с других точек зрения, таких как осознание культуры высокого и низкого контекста, осознанных и бездумных барьеров слушания.

Ключевые слова: умение, общение, язык, подходы к обучению, понимание.

Giyasova Dilafruz KhamzaevnaSenior Lecturer at Samarkand state institute of foreign languages
giyasovadilafruzsam@gmail.com

THE IMPORTANCE OF LISTENING SKILLS IN TEACHING ENGLISH IN ESL CLASSES

ABSTRACT

There is an increasing conviction among ESL teachers that listening comprehension is pivotal in the acquisition of a second language and listening skills ought, therefore, to be taught. The article investigates the importance of listening skills and its role in teaching English in ESL classes. The article provides the pros and cons of different teaching approaches used by teachers and investigate how important is teaching listening from other perspectives, like awareness of high and low context culture, mindful and mindless listening barriers.

Keywords: skill, communication, language, teaching approaches, comprehension

Listening is the important component of interpersonal communication. Effective listening skills are very important on different stages of our life, like family, work, friendship, relatives. Through the listening skills, we understand perspectives of other people, their thoughts and beliefs, feelings, attitudes. As far as communication between co-workers are crucial, listening take first place at work, because proper understanding of perspectives and goals of company will bring to adequate behavior and which is very important to success. Not less important the listening in the family, friendship and between relatives whereas the thoughts, feelings of communicator should be understood appropriately. Systematic investigation of listening comprehension as a skill was not of a great concern until the 1970s. There is an increasing conviction among ESL teachers that listening comprehension is pivotal in the acquisition of a second language and listening skills ought, therefore, to be taught [2, p.15]. As language teachers, we need to think of how we can incorporate listening into our teaching and provide opportunities both inside and outside the classroom for our students to be exposed to significant listening input [3]. According to L.V. Shcherba only a professional who is master in linguistics can teach a language [4]. In teaching listening L. Vandergrift states that while listening one bases on his or her linguistic, pragmatic and prior knowledge [5]. While listening we do comprehend what was said relying on our knowledge of linguistic structures and functions notes P. N. Karimvand [8].

In the article I would like to discuss the pros and cons of different teaching approaches used by teachers and bring some my investigations about how important is teaching listening from other perspectives, like awareness of high and low context culture, mindful and mindless listening barriers.

In recent years, teaching methodology has been developed toward student-centered approach. As it is mentioned in "Interplay: The process of Interpersonal communication" hearing is the process in which sound waves strike the eardrum and cause vibrations that are transmitted to brain [1, p.155]. In daily routine we hear different sounds coming from outside which we cannot influence. At home air conditioner, children playing outside, highway sounds and variety of sounds around us. We usually do not pay much attention to such kind of sounds, as it is mentioned above, it is just sound waves strike the eardrums and cause vibration. Being aware of the process of speech act is crucial because it gives the reason what listeners do while they listen. Scholars state that speech is a multi-level process which requires varied skills for listener to recognize the speech act. Based on V.B. Kasevich we distinguish three levels of speech perception: psychoacoustic, linguistic and cognitive [6]. So, listening requires the knowledge of linguistic and non-linguistic use. Here we can bring another example when I am really tired after long day coming home, trying to relax, my daughter starts telling me about her day I do unconsciously not listen or miss some sentences. I know she is speaking, words are striking my eardrums, but there is no meaning at all. On contrast to hearing, listening occurs when the brain reconstructs the electronic impulses into a representation of the original sound and then gives them meaning [1, p.201]. Listening is more than a strike of waves to eardrums, it is the understanding of one's idea, perspective, outlining priorities. Listening is very important at home, workplace, in creating friendship. While listening it is very crucial to take into consideration the culture and background of person as well. For example, American people are a low context people when they say "NO" it means no, while Uzbek belong to a high context culture, when we say "NO"

it means may be or we want it but just because of shame, we say no. When an American friend of mine offered me food, I said no thanks, but wanted to eat, she just didn't give it to me.

Moreover, there are different listening styles which are important in all stages of our life. "Task oriented listening is most concerned with efficiency and accomplishing the job at hand. When deadlines and other pressures demand immediate action, task orientation can be beneficial" [1, p.201]. As for me I am impatient with people who doesn't go straight to the point during the conversation. I like getting to the point with my family, friends, at school and work. The question I always have is What is the problem/issue or What do you want.

Relational listening is most concerned with building emotional closeness with others. People primarily use this style are typically extroverted, attentive, and friendly. It is difficult for me to understand the emotions and the mood of the speaker. When I talk with my daughter, I try to understand her feelings from her point of view and be with her no matter what. She is in her teenage, so I want to make sure that she feels support from me in dealing with her concerns. Analytical listening emphasizes to the full message before coming to judgement. People who default to this style want to hear details and analyze an issue from a variety of perspectives [1, p.205]. I always hurry to make decisions and form opinions about people, but don't have enough patience to listen up to the end. This is the weakest point in my listening skills which needs more attention. People whose default mode is critical listening have a strong desire to evaluate messages. They are concerned not just with understanding messages but with assessing their quality, focusing on accuracy and consistency. At school and at work I always listen to what was said, what is the agenda for their talk, and unconsciously start noticing errors, misleading speech. As I told before I am impatient with what should be improved.

Another challenge of listening is that there are common barriers of listening like information overload, personal concerns, rapid thoughts and noise. Recognizing all these barriers would possibly help to avoid the poor listening. The information overload which occurs in our daily routine, we are bombarded with information, which makes our attention low. The flow of information we get through the internet, TV, face-to-face makes us listen mindlessly rather than mindfully. On top of all these we have our personal concerns and rapid thoughts like family and work issues, feelings, health and so on. Depending on communicative needs of different level learners English language content should be taught [9]. According to the article of Yang Liu, Xue Bai, Lei Han and Zihan Gao, North China Electric Power University (Baoding), "A Study of English Listening Barrier and Effective Solutions" provided to 2016 International Conference on Education, Management and Applied Social Science Listening barriers are divided into two factors: linguistic and nonlinguistic [7]. Voice disturbance, grammar problem, shortage of vocabulary is determined as a linguistic factor, while lack of cultural background, mental barrier, weak listening skills are nonlinguistic factors. All of these factors play great role in listening skills, because the lack of one of them can insult good listening skills, while being aware of when you engaged in them can help to improve listening skills.

There are five elements of mindful listening: hearing, attending, understanding, remembering, and responding. G.A. Miller and J.A. Selfridge states: «The listener begins with the assumption of a signal at the input. On the basis of this assumption he generates an internal signal to be compared with the perceived one» [10].

Hearing is the most important element of listening, because it gives way to listening. This is the physiological process when sound strikes the eardrums. As mentioned above, the daily information is overloading and the attending is a psychological one, when we decide what information to listen to and which one to skip. The third element of mindful listening is understanding which is no less important. Understanding requires the knowledge of vocabulary, grammar, culture, slang and etc. in order correctly encode the message which has been decoded. The next component is remembering, the ability to recall the information once we have understood it. Early researches showed that people forget the half of what they have heard immediately after hearing it. The last element of listening is responding, which is crucial in mindful listening, because people who listen usually ask questions, give their opinion about what was said [2, p.35].

References:

1. Adler, Rosenfeld, and Proctor, “Interplay: The process of Interpersonal communication” 14 Edition, Oxford University press, 2018.
2. Cindy L. Invitation to Public Speaking Handbook, Griffin, Colorado State University, Wadworth printed in USA 2011.
3. <https://coerll.utexas.edu/methods/modules/listening/01/>.
4. Shcherba, L. V., 1974, Teaching foreign languages at secondary school: general problems of teaching methods. Edited by E. V. Rakhmanova. Moscow. Vysshaya Shkola. 111 p
5. Vandergrift, L., 2009, October, 17, Listening: Theory and practice in modern foreign language competence. Retrieved from <https://www.llas.ac.uk/resources/gpg/67>
6. Kasevich, V. B. (2010). Speech perception. Philosophy of the language. Perm: Perm Scientific Centre URo RAN, 28-32.
7. Y. Liu, X. Bai, and others, North China Electric Power University (Baoding), “A Study of English Listening Barrier and Effective Solutions”, 2016 International Conference on Education, Management and Applied Social Science.
8. Karimvand, P. N. (2011). Psycholinguistic Perspectives on Comprehension in Second Language Acquisition. Journal of Language Teaching and Research, 2 (6), 1268-1273.
9. Leech, G. (2001, April 23) The Role of Frequency in ELT. Direct access: http://www.lancaster.ac.uk/fass/doc_library/linguistics/leechg/leech_2001.pdf
10. Miller, G. A. & Selfridge, J. A. (1950). Verbal context and the recall of meaningful material. American Journal of Psychology, 63, 176-175.

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

5 ЖИЛД, 6 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

ТОМ 5, НОМЕР 6

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 5, ISSUE 6

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000